

Deferred Tax Expense, Tax Planning, and Earnings Management: A Panel Data Analysis

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 30 December 2025	This study investigates the impact of deferred tax expense and tax planning on earnings management in processed food manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period. The study uses secondary data derived from companies' annual reports. The research population consists of 160 financial statements of listed companies, from which 90 firm-year observations were selected using purposive sampling. Panel data regression analysis was performed using EViews 12. The findings reveal that deferred tax expense has a significant effect on earnings management, while tax planning does not have a significant influence on earnings management.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Financial statements provide structured information regarding a firm's financial position and performance over a specific accounting period. Among the various indicators used to assess corporate performance, earnings information plays a central role, as it is widely employed by investors, creditors, and other stakeholders in economic decision-making.

In corporate financial management, the adoption of appropriate accounting and financial policies is expected to support business sustainability and reflect the quality of managerial performance through the achievement of earnings targets. However, in practice, such conditions may incentivize managers to engage in opportunistic behavior in the recognition and reporting of earnings, a practice commonly referred to as earnings management.

Earnings management is defined as managerial actions that deliberately intervene in the financial reporting process by altering, obscuring, or manipulating accounting figures through the application of specific accounting methods and procedures (Sulistiyanto, 2008). Such practices may undermine the fundamental role of financial statements as a reliable communication medium between management and external stakeholders, as the reported information may no longer faithfully represent the firm's underlying economic condition. Consequently, earnings management has become a critical issue in financial reporting, as it can lead to information distortion and adversely affect users of financial statements. This phenomenon is closely associated with information asymmetry, which arises when managers

possess superior information relative to shareholders and other stakeholders (Hairu, 2009).

Empirical evidence of earnings management can be observed in the case of PT Tiga Pilar Sejahtera Food Tbk (AISA). An investigation into the company's 2017 financial statements revealed alleged overstatements totaling approximately Rp4 trillion, attributed to the former management across several accounting items. According to the Fact-Based Investigation Report submitted by Ernst & Young Indonesia to the new management on March 12, 2019, the overstatements were identified in trade receivables, inventories, and fixed assets within the AISA Group. Following the appointment of new management through an Extraordinary General Meeting of Shareholders in October 2018, additional findings indicated revenue overstatements of Rp662 billion and EBITDA overstatements of Rp329 billion in the company's food business segment (CNBC Indonesia).

Prior literature suggests that deferred tax expense can serve as a useful indicator for detecting earnings management. Phillips et al. (2003) argue that deferred tax expense is particularly effective in identifying earnings management undertaken to avoid earnings declines, loss reporting, or failure to meet analysts' earnings forecasts. Their findings indicate that deferred tax expense outperforms traditional accrual-based and forward-looking models in detecting earnings management related to earnings-decrease avoidance. Similarly, in the context of loss avoidance, deferred tax expense has been shown to

provide stronger detection power than accrual-based measures.

From a tax perspective, tax planning represents an integral component of corporate tax management. Suandy (2008) defines tax planning as a structured effort to minimize tax liabilities by exploiting provisions within existing tax regulations, although such practices may diverge from the original intent of lawmakers. The relationship between tax planning and earnings management can be explained by Positive Accounting Theory, particularly the Political Cost Hypothesis. This hypothesis posits that firms exposed to higher political costs tend to engage in income-decreasing earnings management to reduce regulatory scrutiny and political pressure, including tax-related costs. Political costs encompass various costs arising from government intervention and regulation, with taxation representing one of the most significant components (Scott, 2003, as cited in Astutik & Mildawati, 2016).

Despite the strong theoretical linkage between deferred tax expense, tax planning, and earnings management, the extant empirical evidence remains inconclusive. A stream of studies documents a significant association between deferred tax expense and earnings management (Andari et al., 2025; Yati et al., 2020; Purnamasari, 2019; Yulianti, 2005; Astutik & Mildawati, 2016; Negara & Suputra, 2017; Pratita, 2017; Mudjiyanti, 2018). In contrast, other studies fail to find a statistically significant effect of deferred tax expense on earnings management (Liman & Sambuaga, 2025; Timuriana & Muhammad, 2015; Fitriany, 2016; Mulyani et al., 2018).

Similarly, prior research provides mixed evidence regarding the effect of tax planning on earnings management. Several studies find that tax planning significantly influences earnings management practices (Qusna & Widodo, 2024; Purnamasari, 2019; Astutik & Mildawati, 2016; Fitriany, 2016; Negara & Suputra, 2017; Pratita, 2017; Mudjiyanti, 2018). Conversely, other studies suggest that tax planning does not have a significant effect on earnings management (Yati et al., 2020; Mulyani et al., 2018).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Effect of Deferred Tax Expense on Earnings Management

Deferred tax expense results from temporary differences between financial accounting income and taxable income. Such differences occur because financial accounting standards allow managerial discretion in the recognition of revenues and expenses, whereas tax regulations impose stricter rules on income and expense recognition. When management possesses a strong understanding of tax regulations, the gap between accounting income and taxable income may be reduced, thereby improving earnings quality.

Temporary differences that lead to higher tax obligations in future periods are recognized as deferred tax liabilities and give rise to deferred tax expense. An increase in deferred tax liabilities is consistent with firms accelerating revenue recognition or postponing expense recognition for financial reporting purposes relative to tax reporting. In contrast, temporary differences that reduce future tax obligations are recognized as deferred tax assets and result in deferred tax benefits. An increase in deferred tax assets indicates earlier recognition of expenses or the deferral of revenues for financial reporting purposes compared with tax reporting (Sumomba, 2012).

Deferred tax expense has been widely used as an indicator to detect earnings management. Phillips et al. (2003) argue that deferred tax expense is effective in identifying earnings management undertaken to achieve three primary objectives: avoiding earnings declines, avoiding loss reporting, and avoiding failure to meet analysts' earnings forecasts. Firms that recognize higher deferred tax expense tend to exhibit a higher likelihood of engaging in earnings management practices.

Empirical evidence supports this argument. Prior studies document a positive association between deferred tax expense and earnings management (Yulianti, 2005; Sumomba, 2012; Hamzah, 2014; Ifada and Wulandari, 2015; Astutik and Mildawati, 2016; Negara and Suputra, 2017; Pratita, 2017).

H1: Deferred tax expense has a significant effect on earnings management in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period.

2.2 The Effect of Tax Planning on Earnings Management

Tax planning represents an initial stage of tax management aimed at estimating tax liabilities and designing strategies to legally minimize tax payments. It refers to the process of structuring business activities and transactions in order to reduce corporate tax burdens while remaining within the boundaries of applicable tax regulations. At the same time, tax planning also involves ensuring that tax obligations are fulfilled accurately, completely, and in a timely manner, thereby preventing inefficient tax-related expenditures.

Financial statement information may be strategically managed by executives to maximize reported earnings and serve managerial interests. Firms often implement tax planning not only to obtain fiscal advantages but also to enhance reported performance, which may increase firm value and attract external financing through equity markets.

Consistent with this view, Widiatmoko and Mayangsari (2016) document a positive relationship between tax planning and earnings management, indicating that firms engaging more intensively in tax planning are more likely to conduct earnings management. This finding suggests that managerial incentives to reduce tax burdens

may coincide with incentives to manipulate accounting earnings.

Because taxes directly reduce profits available for distribution to shareholders or reinvestment, management has strong incentives to minimize tax expenses in order to maximize net income. Prior empirical studies provide evidence that tax planning is positively associated with earnings management (Sumomba, 2012; Astutik and Mildawati, 2016; Fitriany, 2016; Negara and Suputra, 2017; Pratita, 2017; Mudjiyanti, 2018).

H2: Tax planning has a significant effect on earnings management in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Object, Population, and Sample

This study examines deferred tax expense and tax planning as the independent variables, with earnings management as the dependent variable. The sample comprises manufacturing firms in the processed food sub-sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) over the 2018–2022 period. The research population includes 160 firm-year observations, from which 90 firm-year observations were selected using a purposive sampling approach.

3.2 Operationalization of Research Variables

1. Deferred Tax Expense

Deferred tax expense refers to the expense resulting from temporary differences between accounting income reported for financial reporting purposes and taxable income used in the determination of corporate income tax (Hartono, 2003).

2. Tax Planning

Tax planning represents an initial step undertaken by taxpayers to minimize tax liabilities in the current and future periods, with the objective of reducing tax payments as efficiently as possible while complying with applicable tax regulations (Astutik and Mildawati, 2016).

3. Earnings Management

Earnings management refers to managerial actions intended to alter, obscure, or manipulate reported financial information through the discretionary use of accounting methods and procedures (Sulisyanto, 2008).

3.3 Data Analysis Method

Panel Data Regression Analysis

The data analysis method employed in this study is panel data regression analysis. Panel data regression combines cross-sectional data, which consist of observations across different firms within the same sector, and time-series data, which involve observations over a specific period of time (Winarno, 2015). This approach allows researchers to analyze both firm-specific and time-specific variations simultaneously.

According to Widarjono (2013), panel data analysis offers several advantages compared to other analytical methods, including the ability to provide a larger number of observations, resulting in higher degrees of freedom and greater estimation efficiency. In addition, panel data regression can help mitigate omitted variable bias by capturing unobservable heterogeneity across firms and over time.

In this study, the cross-sectional dimension consists of manufacturing companies in the processed food sub-sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), while the time-series dimension covers the five-year period from 2018 to 2022. The independent variables—deferred tax expense and tax planning—are analyzed to examine their effects on the dependent variable, namely earnings management, using panel data regression techniques.

Widarjono (2013) identifies three main approaches commonly used in panel data regression analysis:

1. Common Effect Model (Pooled Least Squares)
This approach assumes that there are no individual or time-specific differences among firms. All observations are pooled, and a single regression equation is estimated without distinguishing between cross-sectional units or time periods.
2. Fixed Effect Model (FEM)
The fixed effect model allows each firm to have a different intercept, capturing firm-specific characteristics that are constant over time, while the slope coefficients are assumed to be the same across firms and periods.
3. Random Effect Model (REM)
The random effects model assumes that unobserved individual-specific effects are randomly distributed and uncorrelated with the explanatory variables. The model decomposes the disturbance term into two components: a cross-sectional (individual-specific) error component and a remainder error that captures both time-series and cross-sectional variation, commonly referred to as the error components model (ECM).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Panel Data Regression Analysis

Panel data regression analysis integrates cross-sectional and time-series data. Cross-sectional data refer to observations across multiple entities at a given point in time, while time-series data represent observations collected over successive periods. This study employs the random effects model to estimate the panel regression, and the empirical results are reported in the following section.

Table 4.1. Panel Data Regression Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.081421	0.061841	1.316618	0.1914
X1	-3.462132	1.130516	-3.062434	0.0029
X2	-0.114576	0.077700	-1.474595	0.1439

Results

Based on the table above, the estimated equation for the common effect table model in this study is as follows:

$$Y = 0.081 - 3.462 X1 - 0.115 X2 + e$$

Y : Earnings management

X1 : Deferred tax expense

X2 : Tax planning

e : Error term

Based on the estimated regression model, the results can be interpreted as follows:

1. The constant term ($\alpha = 0.081$) indicates that when the independent variables—deferred tax expense and tax planning—are assumed to be constant at zero, earnings management has a value of 0.081.
2. The regression coefficient of deferred tax expense ($\beta_1 = -3.462$) indicates that a one-unit increase in deferred tax expense, while holding tax planning constant, leads to a decrease in earnings management of 3.462 units.
3. The regression coefficient of tax planning ($\beta_2 = -0.115$) indicates that a one-unit increase in tax planning, while holding deferred tax expense constant, results in a decrease in earnings management of 0.115 units.

1. The Effect of Deferred Tax Expense on Earnings Management

The results of the hypothesis testing on the effect of deferred tax expense on earnings management are presented in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2 Results of the Deferred Tax Expense Test on Earnings Management

Tcount	Prob.	Ttable
3,062	0,0029	1,9876

Source: Eviews Program Data Processing Results (2024)

The results in Table 4.2 show that the t-statistic (3.062) exceeds the critical value (1.9876) with a significance level of 0.0029, indicating a significant effect of deferred tax expense on earnings management in processed food manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period.

2. The Effect of Tax Planning on Earnings Management

The results of the hypothesis testing on the effect of tax planning on earnings management are presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3. Results of the Tax Planning Effect Test on Earnings Management

Tcount	Prob.	Ttable
1.4746	0,1439	1,9876

Source: Eviews Program Data Processing Results (2024)

Based on the results presented in Table 4.3, the t-statistic is lower than the critical t-value ($1.4746 < 1.9876$), and the significance level exceeds the 5% threshold ($p\text{-value} = 0.1439 > 0.05$). Therefore, tax planning does not have a significant effect on earnings management in processed food manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period.

4.1.1 Coefficient of Determination

Table 4.4. Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

R-squared	0.110696	Mean dependent var	0.007616
Adjusted R-squared	0.090253	S.D. dependent var	0.333281
S.E. of regression	0.317885	Akaike info criterion	0.578514
Sum squared resid	8.791451	Schwarz criterion	0.661841
Log likelihood	-23.03312	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.612116
F-statistic	5.414676	Durbin-Watson stat	1.998942
Prob(F-statistic)	0.006077		

Source: Eviews Program Data Processing Results (2024)

Based on the table above, the R-squared value is 0.090, indicating that deferred tax expense and tax planning explain only 9% of the variation in earnings management. The remaining 91% of the variation is attributable to other factors not included in the research model.

4.2 Discussion of Research Findings

4.2.1 The Effect of Deferred Tax Expense on Earnings Management

The empirical results indicate that deferred tax expense has a significant effect on earnings management in processed food manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period. This finding suggests that deferred tax expense may serve as an indicator of earnings management practices within the sampled firms.

Temporary differences that give rise to future tax obligations are recognized as deferred tax liabilities and subsequently recorded as deferred tax expense. Such conditions generally occur when firms recognize revenues earlier or defer expenses for financial reporting purposes relative to tax reporting. Conversely, temporary differences that reduce future tax payments are recognized as deferred tax assets, indicating deferred tax benefits. This situation arises when expenses are recognized earlier or revenues are deferred in financial statements compared to tax reporting (Sumomba, 2012).

Deferred tax expense has been widely discussed in the literature as a signal of earnings management. Phillips et al. (2003) argue that deferred tax expense can be used to detect

earnings management activities undertaken to achieve three primary objectives: avoiding earnings declines, avoiding loss reporting, and avoiding failure to meet analysts' earnings forecasts. Accordingly, a higher level of deferred tax expense reflects a greater likelihood that firms engage in earnings management practices.

The findings of this study are consistent with prior empirical research documenting a significant relationship between deferred tax expense and earnings management (Yulianti, 2005; Astutik and Mildawati, 2016; Negara and Suputra, 2017; Pratita, 2017; Mudjiyanti, 2018; Purnamasari, 2019; Yati et al., 2020; Andari et al., 2025).

4.2.2 The Effect of Tax Planning on Earnings Management

The results indicate that tax planning does not have a significant effect on earnings management in processed food manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018–2022 period. This finding suggests that tax planning activities do not play a determining role in earnings management practices within the observed firms.

One possible explanation for this result lies in the different orientations of tax planning and earnings management. Tax planning primarily focuses on legally optimizing tax liabilities in compliance with prevailing tax regulations, whereas earnings management is more closely related to short-term financial reporting objectives, such as meeting earnings targets or maintaining corporate reputation. In addition, strict tax supervision and enforcement, along with other dominant factors—such as capital market pressure, managerial compensation schemes, and audit quality—may reduce the influence of tax planning on earnings management behavior.

This finding is consistent with previous studies reporting no significant relationship between tax planning and earnings management (Yati et al., 2020; Mulyani et al., 2018).

IV. CONCLUSION

1. Deferred tax expense has a significant effect on earnings management, indicating its role as an indicator of earnings management practices.
2. Tax planning does not have a significant effect on earnings management, suggesting it is mainly aimed at tax efficiency and compliance.

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